

I. Think&Feel

What do I think and feel about food waste?

1. How do you feel when you throw away food (e.g., guilt, indifference, responsibility)?

I feel very bad. I feel guilty when I think about the entire process behind it. My values and concerns about the state of the planet make me experience negative emotions toward food waste.

2. How do you feel when you see others wasting food, and what thoughts does this provoke?

I feel the same as before. Moreover, I feel frustrated with people who do not understand the importance of this issue or those who do understand but fail to act accordingly. Many people simply don't think about it.

3. How does food waste align or conflict with your personal values (e.g., sustainability, resourcefulness, temperance-oriented behavior)?

Food waste does not align with my personal values. First and foremost, I do not consider it ethical to waste precious resources.

4. What do you think about the resources (money, energy, labor, natural resources) that go into producing food that gets wasted, and how does that align with your sense of fairness or ethics?

I feel sorry for those resources. I believe that food is purchased excessively, often due to a lack of awareness.

5. What do you think are the main causes of food waste (in your case and in general)?

- *Lack of education leading to a lack of awareness about this global issue.
- *Problems that do not affect us personally tend to be ignored—indifference.
- *Economic prosperity leading to excessive purchasing.
- *An abundance of promotional offers.
- *The sheer variety and abundance of food.
- *Instant gratification and personal indulgences.
- *Lack of respect and the ease of making careless economic decisions (ordering too much).
- *Personal comfort.
- *Lack of time, energy, and exhaustion.

II. See

What food waste patterns / behaviors do I see?

1. Have you noticed any behavior patterns (positive and negative) (please mention them) related to food waste that are common among people in your community or workplace?

Yes, I have:

Positive

*I see people who are concerned about this issue.

*I see people who, even if they don't know much, are willing to learn from others. There is an openness to these problems, and awareness is growing.

Negative

*I see people with conservative tendencies (old habits that lead to food waste).

*People prioritize other things and pay little attention to environmental issues.

2. What motivates people in your surroundings to minimize food waste?

Different reasons:

*Financial savings.

*Concern for the environment.

*Awareness that the world is not heading in a positive direction and a desire to take action.

3. Have you observed any external factors (e.g., portion sizes, expiration dates, packaging) leading to other people's food waste?

Maybe excessive packaging, portion sizes, and office meal orders. All these factors contribute to people's food waste.

III. Say & Do

What do I say and do about food waste?

Own behavior:

1. Have you personally taken any steps to reduce food waste at home? If yes, what are they?

Yes, I have:

- *I eat even slightly older food. I try to have a conscious and informed consumption, by checking labels.
- *I use food preservation methods, such as freezing.
- *I plan my cooking.
- *I cook using leftovers.
- *I buy consciously, based on my needs.
- *I purchase non-perishable items when possible.
- *I educate myself on this topic and remain open to new solutions. I am proactive, seeking out communities to share best practices and learn from.

Obstacles

2. What are your main obstacles or difficulties in trying to reduce your food waste?

Sometimes, procrastination and unpredictable situations.

Motivations

3. What motivates you to avoid your food waste (e.g., saving money, protecting the environment)?

Foremost, it is a question of mindset, the desire to leave things in the same or a better state than I found them. I think about my personal impact and the desire to do better. I'm also concerned about natural resources.

IV. Hear

What do I hear about food waste?

1. Where do you get information about food waste and its impact (e.g., social media, news, campaigns)?

From the internet, through personal searches, and from my friend.

2. Have you ever been inspired by someone else's actions to reduce your food waste?

Yes, by my friend, who is very aware and proactive on environmental issues.

3. Please name two sources of information you trust most to help you avoid food waste.

My friend and, generally, the vegan communities from multiple Facebook groups.

Demographic variables:

Age: 48

Gender: Female

Education: University

Average monthly income for the whole family: 5001-7000 lei/month

Residence: Urban

I have children: Yes

Religion: Agnostic

P2

I. Think&Feel

What do I think and feel about food waste?

1. How do you feel when you throw away food (e.g., guilt, indifference, responsibility)?

I feel guilty. Not as bad, because we have dogs. But I generally don't feel good about it. I also get publicly shamed by my boyfriend. I feel embarrassment.

2. How do you feel when you see others wasting food, and what thoughts does this provoke?

I feel the same. I know that other people's actions are out of my control, but it still doesn't feel right. I feel hopeless.

3. How does food waste align or conflict with your personal values (e.g., sustainability, resourcefulness, temperance-oriented behavior)?

I believe it is not right. I feel aware of the issue and I care about it. I would like us to waste less.

4. What do you think about the resources (money, energy, labor, natural resources) that go into producing food that gets wasted, and how does that align with your sense of fairness or ethics?

I find it sad that we waste so much. I try to connect more with the people I buy from and make more conscious choices. I buy locally and try to avoid purchasing from far away.

5. What do you think are the main causes of food waste (in your case and in general)?

*Education.

*Unplanned shopping.

*Excessive purchasing.

*In Romania, it's also tied to the country's history and the psychological trauma that remains.

II. See

What food waste patterns / behaviors do I see?

1. Have you noticed any behavior patterns (positive and negative) (please mention them) related to food waste that are common among people in your community or workplace?

Positive:

*Someone in my community cooks every Friday using only what's left in the fridge.

*Food that doesn't look perfect is still consumed, including wilted vegetables. Awareness on this topic is growing.

*Vegetable peels and scraps are reused.

Negative:

*Impulsive cravings.

2. What motivates people in your surroundings to minimize food waste?

I believe that moral values and education increase awareness on this topic and motivate people to minimize it.

3. Have you observed any external factors (e.g., portion sizes, expiration dates, packaging) leading to other people's food waste?

I would say packaging and portion sizes.

III. Say & Do

What do I say and do about food waste?

Own behavior:

1. Have you personally taken any steps to reduce food waste at home? If yes, what are they?

Yes:

*Meal planning.

*I don't shop until I've used up what's in the fridge—conscious shopping. I shop frequently but in smaller amounts and locally.

Obstacles

2. What are your main obstacles or difficulties in trying to reduce your food waste?

*Lack of energy and time.

*The need to consciously put in effort and not get caught up in other priorities.

Motivations

3. What motivates you to avoid your food waste (e.g., saving money, protecting the environment)?

*Awareness of the issue.

*Wasting money, resources, and effort.

*The desire to do better.

IV. Hear

What do I hear about food waste?

1. Where do you get information about food waste and its impact (e.g., social media, news, campaigns)?

On social media mostly. I follow organizations or individuals knowledgeable in this field.

2. Have you ever been inspired by someone else's actions to reduce your food waste?

People who cook creatively and waste very little.

3. Please name two sources of information you trust most to help you avoid food waste.

From social media, Roxana Farm and Food Waste Combat.

Demographic variables:

Age: 32

Gender: Female

Education: University

Average monthly income for the whole family: 5001-7000 lei/month

Residence: Rural

I have children: No

Religion: Agnostic

P3

I. Think&Feel

What do I think and feel about food waste?

1. How do you feel when you throw away food (e.g., guilt, indifference, responsibility)?

I feel bad, like I'm making a complete waste of resources. Especially since I was raised in a family where food was rarely thrown away.

2. How do you feel when you see others wasting food, and what thoughts does this provoke?

I feel sadness and frustration. Sadness for the wasted resources and frustration that people are unaware of alternative ways to use food instead of just throwing it in the trash.

3. How does food waste align or conflict with your personal values (e.g., sustainability, resourcefulness, temperance-oriented behavior)?

It completely contradicts my personal values. I consider myself a fair person, and wasting resources is a problem in that sense. In general, I don't agree with any kind of waste, especially since we can't afford to waste anything. I also feel empathy for those who have less.

4. What do you think about the resources (money, energy, labor, natural resources) that go into producing food that gets wasted, and how does that align with your sense of fairness or ethics?

I feel empathy for local producers and all the work behind food production. I also feel guilty because their efforts are not fully respected. I don't think it's fair.

5. What do you think are the main causes of food waste (in your case and in general)?

*Lack of information—education.

*Treating the issue superficially—lack of awareness and indifference.

*Abundance and economic factors that allow us to have more than we actually need.

II. See

What food waste patterns / behaviors do I see?

1. Have you noticed any behavior patterns (positive and negative) (please mention them) related to food waste that are common among people in your community or workplace?

Positive:

- *Meal portions are planned consciously based on needs.
- *Cooking is done for multiple people in a planned manner.

Negative:

- *People discard food when they don't finish their portion, without considering alternatives.
- *Excessive shopping—buying too much inevitably leads to waste.

2. What motivates people in your surroundings to minimize food waste?

- *Financial losses, especially since food has become expensive.
- *Health, both medical and aesthetic reasons.
- *Personal values, such as fairness, frugality, empathy, and the education received from parents.
- *Concern for the environment and resource conservation.

3. Have you observed any external factors (e.g., portion sizes, expiration dates, packaging) leading to other people's food waste?

- *The way food is marketed, because many promotions create an illusion of abundance.
- *Packaging, as large quantities that are hard to consume in time.
- *Short expiration dates on food labels.

III. Say & Do

What do I say and do about food waste?

Own behavior:

1. Have you personally taken any steps to reduce food waste at home? If yes, what are they?

- *Cooking smaller, well-planned portions.
- *Buying only what is strictly necessary, shopping more frequently but in smaller amounts.
- *Avoiding grocery shopping when hungry.
- *Meal planning.
- *Preserving food for as long as possible.

Obstacles

2. What are your main obstacles or difficulties in trying to reduce your food waste?

- *Products in stores come in large sizes and spoil quickly.
- *Many foods are not available in bulk packaging.
- *Sometimes, lack of time.
- *Stress.
- *Lack of facilities where food can be composted.

Motivations

3. What motivates you to avoid your food waste (e.g., saving money, protecting the environment)?

- *Financial reasons.
- *Resource conservation.
- *Awareness that Earth's resources are limited.
- *Moral values.

IV. Hear

What do I hear about food waste?

1. Where do you get information about food waste and its impact (e.g., social media, news, campaigns)?

- *News.
- *Specialized articles.

*Social media.

*Information from my workplace.

2. Have you ever been inspired by someone else's actions to reduce your food waste?

My mother, first and foremost, and my family in general.

3. Please name two sources of information you trust most to help you avoid food waste.

*Specialized workshops at my workplace.

*Scientific articles.

Demographic variables:

Age: 29

Gender: Female

Education: University

Average monthly income for the whole family: 5001-7000 lei/month

Residence: Urban

I have children: No

Religion: Christian orthodox

P4

I. Think&Feel

What do I think and feel about food waste?

1. How do you feel when you throw away food (e.g., guilt, indifference, responsibility)?

I feel unpleasant, as if I'm throwing money in the trash. I feel guilty knowing how much effort goes into producing food.

2. How do you feel when you see others wasting food, and what thoughts does this provoke?

I feel the same way.

3. How does food waste align or conflict with your personal values (e.g., sustainability, resourcefulness, temperance-oriented behavior)?

It does not align with my values at all. I try to minimize all types of waste and be conscious of my impact.

4. What do you think about the resources (money, energy, labor, natural resources) that go into producing food that gets wasted, and how does that align with your sense of fairness or ethics?

I don't believe that any form of waste is positive or fair.

5. What do you think are the main causes of food waste (in your case and in general)?

- *Shopping while hungry.
- *Unplanned shopping without a list.
- *Receiving excessive amounts of food from others.
- *Impulse cravings.
- *The desire to have a full fridge—economic abundance.
- *Preference for eating only the freshest food.
- *Ordering excessive amounts of food.

II. See

What food waste patterns / behaviors do I see?

1. Have you noticed any behavior patterns (positive and negative) (please mention them) related to food waste that are common among people in your community or workplace?

Positive:

- *At work, we cook more at home and bring food instead of ordering excessive amounts.
- *Workplace awareness initiatives.
- *At home, needs are considered more carefully.

Negative:

* I can't think of any negative behavior right now.

2. What motivates people in your surroundings to minimize food waste?

Mainly financial reasons, rather than environmental concerns.

3. Have you observed any external factors (e.g., portion sizes, expiration dates, packaging) leading to other people's food waste?

*Restaurants serve overly large portions, leading to inevitable waste.

*Traditions, such as birthdays, result in excessive food purchases and cooking.

*Lack of awareness about labels (expiration dates vs. "best before" dates).

III. Say & Do

What do I say and do about food waste?

Own behavior:

1. Have you personally taken any steps to reduce food waste at home? If yes, what are they?

*I try to use as much of the product as possible before discarding it.

*Conscious cooking.

Obstacles

2. What are your main obstacles or difficulties in trying to reduce your food waste?

*Lack of facilities for separate waste collection or composting.

*Living conditions—if I had a house with a yard, I would have more options to use food scraps (compost, animals).

*Lack of education.

Motivations

3. What motivates you to avoid your food waste (e.g., saving money, protecting the environment)?

*The possibility of a better world with a cleaner air, a greater environmental care.

*Health.

*Financial savings.

IV. Hear

What do I hear about food waste?

1. Where do you get information about food waste and its impact (e.g., social media, news, campaigns)?

*Personal research.

*Workplace.

*Social media.

2. Have you ever been inspired by someone else's actions to reduce your food waste?

Yes, from people organizing environmental initiatives at my workplace.

3. Please name two sources of information you trust most to help you avoid food waste.

*News from tv channels.

*Workplace.

Demographic variables:

Age: 46

Gender: Female

Education: University

Average monthly income for the whole family: more than 7001 lei

Residence: Urban

I have children: Yes

Religion: Christian (orthodox)

I. Think&Feel

What do I think and feel about food waste?

1. How do you feel when you throw away food (e.g., guilt, indifference, responsibility)?

Guilty. I feel bad. I realize that not everyone has access to food. Animal products are hard to obtain and require a lot of resources. I choose meat over potatoes, but I don't know if that actually helps. I grew up with the idea that you must finish everything on your plate, which creates a compulsion for me, but I don't feel good about it. I also find it hard to plan my meals.

2. How do you feel when you see others wasting food, and what thoughts does this provoke?

Anger, I feel upset that food is being thrown away. Once food has been harvested in some form, it still gets wasted. Waste can happen in multiple ways. I'm not very informed on this topic. It feels as if I were the one throwing that food away. It puts me in a counterproductive mindset.

3. How does food waste align or conflict with your personal values (e.g., sustainability, resourcefulness, temperance-oriented behavior)?

I wouldn't say I'm a consumerist, and I don't like throwing food in the trash. I generally don't resonate with waste. I would like to have a solution to this problem—an option that is the right one, without requiring too much time and energy. Systemic and convenient solutions.

It aligns with my values—I don't like wasting food. But I find it very difficult to avoid. There aren't easy solutions.

4. What do you think about the resources (money, energy, labor, natural resources) that go into producing food that gets wasted, and how does that align with your sense of fairness or ethics?

It doesn't seem fair. Waste exists in nature anyway—it's something natural. Entropy increases at the expense of order. The problem arises when this waste is not natural, but resources are used inefficiently to produce food. I have a tendency to judge nonsense things.

5. What do you think are the main causes of food waste (in your case and in general)?

*When basic goods have a low cost, your perception of their value decreases. Lack of awareness and devaluation due to economic well-being.

*In the last century, the driving force has been purely economic. Sustainability factors are not taken into account. The major macro-themes are focused on something else.

*There seems to be a correlation between a country's economy and other spheres such as politics and military aspects. Sustainability issues are not always aligned with economic interests.

II. See

What food waste patterns / behaviors do I see?

1. Have you noticed any behavior patterns (positive and negative) (please mention them) related to food waste that are common among people in your community or workplace?

Positive:

*It's not inherently negative, but I don't throw things away immediately. I try to be mindful, and I see this in those close to me as well.

*At work, for example, people are open to being made aware of this issue and would like to do things differently.

Negative:

*Food is thrown away so quickly that you don't even have time to process it. A general lack of awareness.

*I observe emotional disconnection to waste.

2. What motivates people in your surroundings to minimize food waste?

The way the question is phrased is a bit biased—it assumes that people are the ones wasting food, rather than the system as a whole. We were born into a system and act based on what we have seen and experienced. It is hard to change something—we have less time and attention nowadays, with social media and other modern distractions. I don't think blaming the individual is fair. We all do what we can in the way we can. Can we do more? Yes. But modern life means having many things to do in a very short time. It's unrealistic to pay attention to everything. Why isn't there an option at restaurants to order by portion size? Why aren't there composting contracts? I don't think people are motivated to waste food. I think people don't know and find it difficult to do otherwise. It's interesting to compare two countries or regions at the same technological level but with different cultural systems—like a Nordic country and Romania. You would see more educated and conscious behaviors. At a different technological level, people haven't grown up in a system designed for high output like modern civilization. Modern civilization is designed to waste. A village consumes resources to survive, but the people there also have skills that connect them with nature. They won't go and defecate in the river that sustains them. Their system is more sustainable, which ironically makes them more sustainable than a modern, educated civilization. One cause is that technological advancement is exponential, so fast that it pushes the adaptability of the human brain beyond its natural limit. Communities learned over a thousand years that it's not good to defecate in a river, and so on. We, as a modern civilization, are only now learning that certain things are bad. There are deeper causes that are not immediately obvious.

3. Have you observed any external factors (e.g., portion sizes, expiration dates, packaging) leading to other people's food waste?

*Restaurant portion sizes. Many people don't correlate weight with a serving size, and portions shouldn't be fixed—you should be able to choose how much and what.

*Differences between expiration date types.

*The system and how it's designed (your surrounding community matters a lot because that's where you pick up behaviors).

*Education.

III. Say & Do

What do I say and do about food waste?

Own behavior:

1. Have you personally taken any steps to reduce food waste at home? If yes, what are they?

*Correct portioning. However, as a biological being (a primate), portioning is directly proportional to hunger. There should be more awareness about how much you actually need, not how much you feel like eating.

*I'm mindful and seek information.

*I know my limit regarding how much food I can keep at home. I buy as much as I consume.

*I consume food close to its "best before" date.

*Food preservation methods.

*Optimizing my personal system—portions, types of food, everything.

Obstacles

2. What are your main obstacles or difficulties in trying to reduce your food waste?

*I buy multiple items at once and can't finish them before they expire. *Unpredictable factors.

*I forget about food in the fridge, and it spoils.

*Weakness in adopting new tactics.

*Changes in appetite. Food quality after reheating. Lack of convenience.

Motivations

3. What motivates you to avoid your food waste (e.g., saving money, protecting the environment)?

*Avoiding guilt. I want to have a net positive impact on the planet. In the current system, it's hard for me to do that. It involves radical changes, and it's not easy for me to change or adapt. I have to mentally reorganize things, and that's difficult for me.

*Financial factors. The middle-ground option, marketing, is a barrier.

*I have a small range of foods I eat, which makes it easier to manage.

IV. Hear

What do I hear about food waste?

1. Where do you get information about food waste and its impact (e.g., social media, news, campaigns)?

Social media, YouTube, depending on my interests at the time.

2. Have you ever been inspired by someone else's actions to reduce your food waste?

No, because their strategies weren't "low-hanging fruit" for me. They came from a familiar environment.

3. Please name two sources of information you trust most to help you avoid food waste.

YouTube channels that I've known for a long time. When I subscribe to a new channel, I check its sources and information. I'm very critical. I look for the scientific method when I watch.

Kurzgesagt, Minute Earth (Minute Food), TED-Ed.

Demographic variables:

Age: 29

Gender: Male

Education: University

Average monthly income for the whole family: 5001 - 7000 lei/month

Residence: Urban

I have children: No

Religion: Atheist

P6

I. Think&Feel

What do I think and feel about food waste?

1. How do you feel when you throw away food (e.g., guilt, indifference, responsibility)?

I feel a sense of guilt. I don't think it's right to throw away food, but I also don't want to overeat and force myself to finish it. I feel guilty and try to be more mindful in the future.

2. How do you feel when you see others wasting food, and what thoughts does this provoke?

I feel understanding towards the situation. If I know that someone is aware of food waste issues and still throws food away, I feel frustrated. But for others, I remain calm and understanding.

3. How does food waste align or conflict with your personal values (e.g., sustainability, resourcefulness, temperance-oriented behavior)?

I don't think it aligns with my values. I don't believe in over-purchasing, but at the same time, I don't want to take extreme measures either.

4. What do you think about the resources (money, energy, labor, natural resources) that go into producing food that gets wasted, and how does that align with your sense of fairness or ethics?

I don't think it's ethical. We don't think enough about this issue. We fall into the comfort of always finding everything we need at the supermarket. I don't consider alternatives like local markets sufficient. I think this topic becomes more important when you have children because you start thinking more about health.

5. What do you think are the main causes of food waste (in your case and in general)?

*In Romania, I believe the communist era contributed to today's behaviors. Past generations experienced scarcity and limited access to resources. These feelings of deprivation have now translated, fueled by economic prosperity, into excessive shopping. The fear of running out of food and rationing still lingers in the Romanian mentality.

*Romanian culture, from traditions to celebrations like barbecues.

*Economic surplus.

*Store promotions that encourage unnecessary purchases.

*All-you-can-eat restaurants.

II. See

What food waste patterns / behaviors do I see?

1. Have you noticed any behavior patterns (positive and negative) (please mention them) related to food waste that are common among people in your community or workplace?

Positive:

*There are workplace initiatives to raise awareness and educate people on sustainability, including food waste.

- *People are becoming more mindful of their health.
- *They buy less but focus on quality.
- *They are drawn to trending topics like sustainability.

Negative:

- *There is still insufficient awareness about this issue.

2. What motivates people in your surroundings to minimize food waste?

- *Financial reasons.
- *The effort spent acquiring resources, which then goes to waste, leads to frustration.

3. Have you observed any external factors (e.g., portion sizes, expiration dates, packaging) leading to other people's food waste?

- *Expiration dates and the lack of education about how to read labels and understand their meaning.
- *Lack of knowledge about food. Some people throw away food that is close to the expiration date because they assume it's no longer fresh.
- *Economic abundance leads to excessive shopping.
- *Picky children who pressure parents into buying extra food.

III. Say & Do

What do I say and do about food waste?

Own behavior:

1. Have you personally taken any steps to reduce food waste at home? If yes, what are they?

- *For fruits that don't look fresh, I dehydrate them or turn them into juices instead of throwing them away. Creative cooking.
- *Freezing food to preserve it longer.
- *Checking my fridge before grocery shopping. Conscious shopping.
- *Planning meals based on needs.

Obstacles

2. What are your main obstacles or difficulties in trying to reduce your food waste?

*Lack of time.

*Lack of energy to cook, which leads to food expiring and being thrown away.

*Other priorities that shift my focus elsewhere.

Motivations

3. What motivates you to avoid your food waste (e.g., saving money, protecting the environment)?

Once I became more aware of the problems caused by food waste, like the amount of water used to produce food, I started caring more about the environment and protecting it.

IV. Hear

What do I hear about food waste?

1. Where do you get information about food waste and its impact (e.g., social media, news, campaigns)?

Social media, educational campaigns, and workplace initiatives.

2. Have you ever been inspired by someone else's actions to reduce your food waste?

Yes, my workplace has been a strong influence.

3. Please name two sources of information you trust most to help you avoid food waste.

YouTube and materials created by experts in the field, as well as workplace resources.

Demographic variables:

Age: 35

Gender: Female

Education: University

Average monthly income for the whole family: 5001 - 7000 lei/month

Residence: Urban

I have children: No

Religion: Christian Orthodox

I. Think&Feel

What do I think and feel about food waste?

1. How do you feel when you throw away food (e.g., guilt, indifference, responsibility)?

I feel responsible for the waste. I think it's my responsibility to plan what I need and how to do better. I often think about how to save what could be saved.

2. How do you feel when you see others wasting food, and what thoughts does this provoke?

I feel sad and disgusted. People, in general, don't realize how much effort goes into producing and transporting food to reach them. I feel sad because I sometimes do the same and throw away food. It has become so easy to throw food away without being aware of it.

3. How does food waste align or conflict with your personal values (e.g., sustainability, resourcefulness, temperance-oriented behavior)?

Food waste goes against my values. Moderation would be the first value that is violated. The second value is respect for the people involved in the food production process. Environmental care is also very important to me.

4. What do you think about the resources (money, energy, labor, natural resources) that go into producing food that gets wasted, and how does that align with your sense of fairness or ethics?

I think the current system is unethical. There is an excess of food supply, which, together with promotional offers, encourages people not to respect the effort that goes into producing, transporting, and distributing food to get it to their refrigerators.

5. What do you think are the main causes of food waste (in your case and in general)?

*People don't control the food they already have before going shopping.

*They don't plan their meals.

*They are attracted by momentary cravings.

*Lack of moderation, buying too much without considering their needs.

*Indifference that leads to a lack of moderation and respect for resources.

*Lack of education.

II. See

What food waste patterns / behaviors do I see?

1. Have you noticed any behavior patterns (positive and negative) (please mention them) related to food waste that are common among people in your community or workplace?

Yes:

Positive

*Less and more mindful shopping.

*Freezing food.

*Meal planning.

*Growing some of your own ingredients, which makes you value them more.

*Cooking at home (personal effort) makes you more conscientious. Consuming food from your own production or higher-quality (organic) food motivates you to waste less.

Negative

*Buying more than needed without checking what's already at home.

*Forgetting to eat or cook food on time, which leads to it spoiling and being thrown away.

*Ordering larger portions than one can eat, or buying too much food in general.

2. What motivates people in your surroundings to minimize food waste?

*Consuming food from personal production or higher-quality (organic) food motivates people to waste less.

*Connecting with the producers (e.g., at the market).

*Protecting the environment, caring for the planet's limited resources.

*The desire not to waste money they've earned.

*Time wastage – whether you've bought food or cooked it, wasting time and money. People are very busy and want to minimize their time losses.

3. Have you observed any external factors (e.g., portion sizes, expiration dates, packaging) leading to other people's food waste?

*Cheap food, processed food that creates the illusion in the consumer's mind that they can afford excess food. (e.g., buying 3 loaves of bread instead of one)

*Expiration dates. Buying too much food that expires quickly. Disorganization and expiration dates lead to waste.

*Store promotions encouraging people to buy more in a short time. (last-minute, super deals)

*Best before dates: Many people think the product is no longer good and just throw it away (e.g., coffee).

*Social pressure in groups to not eat too much and leaving food on their plates (especially for those with extra weight). Generally, people don't eat everything. They try food, and if they don't like it, they throw it away. They buy more to impress others (holidays, special occasions).

*Food display policies (e.g., buffet-style restaurants): The food display always appears abundant to attract customers, but by the end of the day, everything gets thrown away.

*Lack of regulations encouraging small producers to process raw food (fruits and vegetables) to save it from waste. What doesn't sell gets thrown away. Too many criteria requiring large investments encourage big producers, not small ones.

*Too much product supply.

*Food with tempting packaging but low nutritional value, which generates hunger, leading to more shopping and increased potential for food waste.

III. Say & Do

What do I say and do about food waste?

Own behavior:

1. Have you personally taken any steps to reduce food waste at home? If yes, what are they?

*I buy less, more consciously, and more often (I have stores nearby).

*I freeze what I can't consume in time (requires a large freezer).

*I optimize the amount of food I cook – planned cooking.

*Before shopping, I check what I already have at home.

*I cook creatively with what food I have at home.

If a recipe calls for a rarely used ingredient, I try to find alternatives I already have at home, or I don't add it to avoid buying it and letting it waste.

*I make preserves to save excess food at the moment.

Obstacles

2. What are your main obstacles or difficulties in trying to reduce your food waste?

*Time. I don't dedicate enough time to optimize what I already have.

*I cook something fresh without consuming what's left in the fridge.

*I forget about some ingredients that expire.

*I put too much food on my plate, and there's not enough left to be considered a portion, which pushes me to cook again.

*Unexpected events when I consume food outside the house instead of at home.

*Small freezer.

*Culinary flexibility that requires more time. The comfort (habit) of always cooking the same recipes.

Motivations

3. What motivates you to avoid your food waste (e.g., saving money, protecting the environment)?

*Fear of losing money.

*Time invested throughout the entire value chain.

*Negative environmental effects. I don't have a composting system; it's not adequately processed and pollutes.

IV. Hear

What do I hear about food waste?

1. Where do you get information about food waste and its impact (e.g., social media, news, campaigns)?

*Scientific articles

*Social media

*Other people

*Documentaries

2. Have you ever been inspired by someone else's actions to reduce your food waste?

I don't think I've been inspired by anyone. I was inspired by a negative example. My mother used to cook a lot and throw away her work. This inspired me to cook more moderately. I was inspired by people close to me who had full refrigerators, and that abundance motivated me to buy more consciously. Effort and money wasted.

3. Please name two sources of information you trust most to help you avoid food waste.

People I know well and appreciate. Any information from scientific sources. Public campaigns launched by NGOs (e.g., Food Waste Combat, Food Bank).

Demographic variables:

Age: 25

Gender: Female

Education: University

Average monthly income for the whole family: 5001 - 7000 lei/month

Residence: Urban

I have children: No

Religion: Atheist

P8

I. Think&Feel

What do I think and feel about food waste?

1. How do you feel when you throw away food (e.g., guilt, indifference, responsibility)?

I feel bad, but on the other hand, I won't force myself to eat just for the sake of eating. I didn't grow up with the culture of eating everything on my plate, but not with excessive waste either.

2. How do you feel when you see others wasting food, and what thoughts does this provoke?

Honestly, not as bad. It seems to me it is everyone's responsibility, especially at home. On the street, it's different; people should be responsible.

3. How does food waste align or conflict with your personal values (e.g., sustainability, resourcefulness, temperance-oriented behavior)?

It does not align. I would say on a scale from 1 to 10, it's an 8. I understand the importance of the issue, and everyone should make efforts in this regard, but on the other hand, I won't force myself to eat when I can't just to avoid throwing food away. Waste comes from various causes; sometimes the planets don't align, or I forget about food and it spoils in the fridge.

4. What do you think about the resources (money, energy, labor, natural resources) that go into producing food that gets wasted, and how does that align with your sense of fairness or ethics?

It seems to me that the problem is more accentuated in supermarkets and restaurants. It's less of an issue at home. In supermarkets and restaurants, the food waste flow is out of control. One thing is to throw away a loaf of bread, another would be throwing away tens of kilograms that each restaurant throws away every day. I don't know if there are initiatives in Romania to donate leftover or near-expiration food, but in other countries, this happens. I would like it to happen more here as well.

5. What do you think are the main causes of food waste (in your case and in general)?

*Overconsumption

*Society has reached a very high level of choice. The accessibility of food is so high that it leads to other micro-causes, like curiosity or momentary cravings.

II. See

What food waste patterns / behaviors do I see?

1. Have you noticed any behavior patterns (positive and negative) (please mention them) related to food waste that are common among people in your community or workplace?

Positive:

*My father works in IT at a company that owns Cocorico, the chicken brand, and there I heard that employees have initiatives. Each of them has a chicken quota per month, and several employees mobilized to donate what remains to an elderly care home.

*I've seen initiatives at restaurants. Food donations, homeless centers. Supermarkets with last-offer zones. It's half-price, and the discount applies. I think this is an implementation initiative to avoid throwing food away when it expires.

Negative:

*Too much is ordered in companies, and leftovers can't even be consumed by the employees at home, even if they take it with them. If it's not thrown away at the company, it's thrown away by the employees.

*At restaurants, some portions are too large, and food is wasted.

*People order just to taste something, then they don't like it and throw it away.

*People buy different brands (chocolate) just because they can, and then throw it away if they don't like it.

*People throw the food away without knowing the label difference. It would be good to test it.

*Young people might throw away more. We grew up without accountability. Our parents grew up in communism. We grew up in economic prosperity and lost respect. From here comes waste in all aspects.

2. What motivates people in your surroundings to minimize food waste?

*Ethical and society-driven motives, like guilt about throwing food away when others don't even have enough to eat. Or respect for resources.

*The financial aspect, the regret of throwing money away.

3. Have you observed any external factors (e.g., portion sizes, expiration dates, packaging) leading to other people's food waste?

*Portion sizes at restaurants.

*The variety of foods of each kind. (Different packaging leads to curiosity)

*Education regarding label differences.

III. Say & Do

What do I say and do about food waste?

Own behavior:

1. Have you personally taken any steps to reduce food waste at home? If yes, what are they?

*Shopping list. Planned shopping.

*Conscious shopping based on needs. Meal planning.

*I check what I have at home and expiration dates.

*I look for ways to better preserve food, like fruits. (Tips and tricks)

Obstacles

2. What are your main obstacles or difficulties in trying to reduce your food waste?

*The temptation of variety in other things.

*The ease and accessibility with which I find food. It's not like in the past when maybe you could only find a loaf of bread and that's it. (Devaluation)

*Unexpected situations, e.g., eating out instead of at home.

Motivations

3. What motivates you to avoid your food waste (e.g., saving money, protecting the environment)?

*Ethical and moral principles. I remind myself of the privilege I have and those who don't have enough food.

*The economic aspect. "I don't like to throw money away."

IV. Hear

What do I hear about food waste?

1. Where do you get information about food waste and its impact (e.g., social media, news, campaigns)?

I don't do it intentionally. If I'm looking for something specific, I'll search it on Google. Otherwise, I see different reels about the topic on social media. Unfortunately, I haven't seen any awareness campaigns on this topic.

2. Have you ever been inspired by someone else's actions to reduce your food waste?

Yes, social media helps me, for example. I remember the actions I can take myself. It inspires me to do the same.

3. Please name two sources of information you trust most to help you avoid food waste.

Google and my life partner, who is strictly passionate about the subject.

Other thoughts following the interview:

- This topic should be discussed more in society. I think both authorities and the ecological side should take it more seriously.
- From us, I don't know if everyone has the same interests or the same moral or ethical principles. Coercive measures work. The state should say don't throw it away. The state can intervene in restaurants, companies, authorities. The problem with ethical issues is that the population's interest is directly proportional to where they are on Maslow's pyramid. Survival comes first. Climate change doesn't. It's a privilege to think about other problems. Those at this level.

Demographic variables:

Age: 28

Gender: Female

Education: University

Average monthly income for the whole family: more than 7001 lei/month

Residence: Urban

I have children: No

Religion: Atheist

I. Think&Feel

What do I think and feel about food waste?

1. How do you feel when you throw away food (e.g., guilt, indifference, responsibility)?

I feel disappointed and ashamed.

2. How do you feel when you see others wasting food, and what thoughts does this provoke?

Reassured that I'm not the only one doing it. It motivates me to be better and not settle. It reminds me that I am part of the problem.

3. How does food waste align or conflict with your personal values (e.g., sustainability, resourcefulness, temperance-oriented behavior)?

It presses some buttons for me. It aligns with some values I still need to work on, like discipline. In general, I'm not for any type of waste. I think that if something can be used, it should be. Food waste is not aligned with my values, so there are moral values, but my actions don't reflect them.

4. What do you think about the resources (money, energy, labor, natural resources) that go into producing food that gets wasted, and how does that align with your sense of fairness or ethics?

It's a problem at the solution level, not at the philosophical level. We need to work on solutions. For example, I need to buy better-quality products and be more mindful of what I use.

5. What do you think are the main causes of food waste (in your case and in general)?

*Personal comfort.

*Disconnection from food. We don't see the effort behind it.

*Economic prosperity and the abundance of offers that leads to excessive shopping.

II. See

What food waste patterns / behaviors do I see?

1. Have you noticed any behavior patterns (positive and negative) (please mention them) related to food waste that are common among people in your community or workplace?

Positive:

*In general, we try to be more aware, so we do better.

*At work, there are colleagues interested in environmental issues.

*The topic of food waste is becoming more important.

*At work, I've noticed some colleagues ordering more and sharing with others so nothing is left behind.

*Supermarkets reduce the price of food to half to avoid food waste.

*Some restaurants or even individuals donate leftover edible food.

Negative:

-

2. What motivates people in your surroundings to minimize food waste?

*Financial resources.

*When you feel a problem affects you directly, like environmental issues.

*Education and awareness about the issue.

*Respect for resources, from work to animals, people, time, and effort.

*Social pressure and the desire for conformity.

3. Have you observed any external factors (e.g., portion sizes, expiration dates, packaging) leading to other people's food waste?

*Portion sizes.

*Food quality. If it's better, people buy less because it's more expensive. If it's worse, they buy excessively.

*People's education. Less educated people buy more mindlessly.

III. Say & Do

What do I say and do about food waste?

Own behavior:

1. Have you personally taken any steps to reduce food waste at home? If yes, what are they?

*Consuming consciously. Connecting with what I eat.

*Cooking with what's left in the fridge.

*Buying more consciously. Better quality, less quantity.

*I eat the same food multiple times to avoid waste, even if I don't like it.

Obstacles

2. What are your main obstacles or difficulties in trying to reduce your food waste?

*Comfort from instant gratification.

*Discipline, or rather the lack of it.

Motivations

3. What motivates you to avoid your food waste (e.g., saving money, protecting the environment)?

*Moral values. To be ethical, disciplined, and temperate.

*The desire to do better.

*The desire to live more mindfully, more consciously.

*Respect for resources.

IV. Hear

What do I hear about food waste?

1. Where do you get information about food waste and its impact (e.g., social media, news, campaigns)?

I don't really take an initiative to look into this topic. I get my information from friends, sources on YouTube, social media like Reddit, Instagram, books, and work.

2. Have you ever been inspired by someone else's actions to reduce your food waste?

I am constantly influenced by my girlfriend, friends, colleagues, what others do, and social media.

3. Please name two sources of information you trust most to help you avoid food waste.

The people close to me, so my girlfriend and friends first. Secondly, books and YouTube.

Demographic variables:

Age: 37

Gender: Male

Education: University

Average monthly income for the whole family: more than 7001 lei/month

Residence: Rural

I have children: No

Religion: Agnostic

P10

I. Think&Feel

What do I think and feel about food waste?

1. How do you feel when you throw away food (e.g., guilt, indifference, responsibility)?

When I throw away a lot of food, I feel bad (guilty). I think about the resources behind the food. I think that the food is no longer useful; it was a waste of resources. I would have liked to have an animal to give the food to, so I wouldn't waste it completely.

2. How do you feel when you see others wasting food, and what thoughts does this provoke?

At first, it's a negative emotion, it makes me very angry and I dislike it. I think about the benefit that food could have had if used differently. My thought would be to tell them not to make so much food just to throw it away. Sometimes, I wish I could sacrifice myself and eat it if it's healthy. If it's unhealthy, I prefer to throw it away so it doesn't harm me.

3. How does food waste align or conflict with your personal values (e.g., sustainability, resourcefulness, temperance-oriented behavior)?

I believe that my values are against food waste. I consider myself an active participant in trying to avoid food waste. I help wherever I can lend a hand. I'm an economical person, and I feel bad about wasting resources. It's better to eat everything.

Many people don't finish their plate because of preference (they didn't like the food much – curious but didn't like it). Society doesn't teach us to respect food. It doesn't make us aware.

4. What do you think about the resources (money, energy, labor, natural resources) that go into producing food that gets wasted, and how does that align with your sense of fairness or ethics?

I think that a more sustainable chain should be created for everyone. There should be more natural food, without processing. Local food. We should invest in what is healthier and better.

There are so many resources invested and then wasted because there is no positive aspect. It's an underoptimized system. It's not fair, companies should plan in more detail where they can make the system more efficient and optimized. It's not right to throw away so many resources.

5. What do you think are the main causes of food waste (in your case and in general)?

*No food planning, how much will be eaten.

*Cases of fads, momentary pleasures.

*Economic prosperity leads to indifference and disrespect for resources.

*More product than consumed (restaurants). *Underoptimization of the system – what happens to what's left.

II. See

What food waste patterns / behaviors do I see?

1. Have you noticed any behavior patterns (positive and negative) (please mention them) related to food waste that are common among people in your community or workplace?

Positive:

- *My parents eat everything so they don't leave anything.
- *I put only as much food on my plate as I think I'll eat and seal the rest.
- *People buy food that expires the quickest (supermarket shelf).

Negative:

- *I forget to eat food.
- *People rely on pleasures and throw food away.
- *Pre-made food comes and is thrown away.

2. What motivates people in your surroundings to minimize food waste?

- *Health, to consume more consciously.
- *Economic aspects.
- *Care for our planet.

3. Have you observed any external factors (e.g., portion sizes, expiration dates, packaging) leading to other people's food waste?

- *Too large portions at restaurants.
- *Ignorance of what and how you eat.

III. Say & Do

What do I say and do about food waste?

Own behavior:

1. Have you personally taken any steps to reduce food waste at home? If yes, what are they?

- *I reduce food shopping.
- *Planned and conscious shopping.

*I've started helping the people close to me to raise awareness about this topic and avoid food waste.

Obstacles

2. What are your main obstacles or difficulties in trying to reduce your food waste?

Negative habits from the past (too much food, better more than less).

Motivations

3. What motivates you to avoid your food waste (e.g., saving money, protecting the environment)?

*To have a better world, to protect our planet.

*To think about the negative effects we cause.

*To think about future generations and maintain natural resources.

*Wasting effort and resources.

*Money invested.

IV. Hear

What do I hear about food waste?

1. Where do you get information about food waste and its impact (e.g., social media, news, campaigns)?

I don't take an initiative to look into this topic. I get informed from social media. I have a few people who have studies in this field. I rarely hear about it on the news. What is heard in the school environment and from people close to me.

2. Have you ever been inspired by someone else's actions to reduce your food waste?

Yes, I was inspired by someone to eat more consciously. To put on my plate as much as I think I'll eat, thinking about how much I need and why I'm eating that much.

3. Please name two sources of information you trust most to help you avoid food waste.

My brother would be the first source, and the second source would be Instagram.

Demographic variables:

Age: 18

Gender: Male

Education: Student

Average monthly income for the whole family: 1001 - 3000 lei/month

Residence: Urban

I have children: No

Religion: Atheist

P11

I. Think&Feel

What do I think and feel about food waste?

1. How do you feel when you throw away food (e.g., guilt, indifference, responsibility)?

I feel wasteful, I feel bad. It seems to me that there is a lot of waste in the world in general, not just in Romania. I feel bad that it's not possible for us to do better.

2. How do you feel when you see others wasting food, and what thoughts does this provoke?

It annoys me, but it depends on the context. I feel sorry that that person wasn't more careful about their actions. I can understand. However, I'm angry with people who throw away food that is still consumable, packaged, in good condition. It annoys me. I remember about the Sânziana Negru case when she discarded food immediately after promoting it on social media.

3. How does food waste align or conflict with your personal values (e.g., sustainability, resourcefulness, temperance-oriented behavior)?

It doesn't align. It's something I don't want to do, only when it's absolutely necessary. If it spoils or is not consumed in time, then I'm forced, with regret, to throw it away. But, otherwise, I don't want to waste it. I try to never waste food. As rarely as possible.

4. What do you think about the resources (money, energy, labor, natural resources) that go into producing food that gets wasted, and how does that align with your sense of fairness or ethics?

It seems dreadful to me. It involves work and time from many people, including machinery and capitalism. It seems like a huge amount of wasted labor. Natural resources are used and they pollute leading to climate change and natural disasters. Production just for the sake of producing as if it were never used. People don't think enough about this topic. They only think on a micro level, without knowing the macro level. People buy just for the sake of buying. People buy unconsciously. People with little money try to portion their food and be more frugal. They think more carefully about whether to buy something. They throw away less due to their own fault.

5. What do you think are the main causes of food waste (in your case and in general)?

*Lack of time. Many people do their shopping and think about how many things they will cook, but then they don't do it. It ends up spoiling in the fridge. Greens, milk, meat, eggs...

*Lack of food planning/organization.

*Personal education, even educated people don't know there are ways to preserve food for longer. These are things missing from our education.

*Lack of education at home.

*Waste due to economic prosperity.

*Waste due to the system (poor regulation). People are forced to throw away food instead of donating it. The food could be used by those who need it more, but it still gets thrown away. There is a lack of strict legal rules to oblige institutions to reduce food waste and use resources better. The distribution chain needs to be rethought.

*Creation of limited supply (spray on donuts). Stupidity.

*Pure malice on the part of people.

*Economic detachment (prosperity – indifference to the lower class).

II. See

What food waste patterns / behaviors do I see?

1. Have you noticed any behavior patterns (positive and negative) (please mention them) related to food waste that are common among people in your community or workplace?

Positive:

*Taking leftover food from a restaurant.

*Grocery products, consuming food even when it's expired.

Negative:

*Products with expiration dates. People don't know the difference between "best before" and the expiration date.

*If a small amount of good food is left, but not enough for a full portion, I throw it away.

2. What motivates people in your surroundings to minimize food waste?

*Finances. Right now, everything has become much more expensive, inflation. We are in a recession. People are more aware because of their spending.

*Ethical reasons. There are so many people who don't have food, so people think about others. You want to be a better person to influence society and the planet in a positive direction. You want to feel like a better person.

*Concern for nature.

*Social pressure. The environment you're in. At the office, you have certain commitments, and you see what others are doing, so you don't throw away leftovers. At home, alone, you might. And in brief contexts, it applies. Visiting a friend for a week (unwanted guest).

3. Have you observed any external factors (e.g., portion sizes, expiration dates, packaging) leading to other people's food waste?

*Portion sizes are too large in some cases.

*Taste: preference for restaurant taste. Allergies and personal choices.

*How much space you have and the conditions for storing food. A small fridge that doesn't work.

*Labels ("best before" – expiration date).

*The package from mom (unpredictable situations).

III. Say & Do

What do I say and do about food waste?

Own behavior:

1. Have you personally taken any steps to reduce food waste at home? If yes, what are they?

*I educate myself on how to store food properly and avoid mistakes, using short videos. Little things and I try to preserve many foods.

*I buy intentionally and planned.

*I don't buy on impulse.

*Food chosen based on experience and personal needs.

*I prefer to buy things I will actually consume. Quality over quantity. I'm careful about what I buy. For example, ready-to-eat avocados.

*I buy in small quantities.

*I freeze food to make it last longer.

Obstacles

2. What are your main obstacles or difficulties in trying to reduce your food waste?

*Life (time, priorities, plans, stress).

*Impulse cravings as a reward after a long, stressful day. Discipline.

*Unavoidable situations (like when a friend calls me out).

Motivations

3. What motivates you to avoid your food waste (e.g., saving money, protecting the environment)?

*The fact that I want to live on a decent planet. Any contribution, no matter how small, helps. The desire to do better.

*It's a privilege to have access to food. I feel bad about it. It's more of a mental thing than an economic one.

*Personal authenticity. I eat strictly what I like.

IV. Hear

What do I hear about food waste?

1. Where do you get information about food waste and its impact (e.g., social media, news, campaigns)?

I don't inform myself proactively; it appears due to algorithms. TikTok, Instagram, YouTube, websites, specialty blogs. I don't do it very often.

2. Have you ever been inspired by someone else's actions to reduce your food waste?

I was inspired by infographics, statistics on how food waste impacts the planet. When you see real, negative things happening, it motivates you. I'm influenced by activists who are involved, and I trust what they say. When more people talk about it, I get a boost of motivation (negative influence: Sânziana Negru). It feels like being scolded.

3. Please name two sources of information you trust most to help you avoid food waste.

Social media and profile blogs, cooking. People passionate about the topic who inform themselves from valid sources.

Demographic variables:

Age: 33

Gender: Female

Education: University

Average monthly income for the whole family: 5001 - 7000 lei/month

Residence: Urban

I have children: No

Religion: Atheist

P12

I. Think&Feel

What do I think and feel about food waste?

1. How do you feel when you throw away food (e.g., guilt, indifference, responsibility)?

I feel very bad, it's like throwing away money, our hard work. When you throw it away, sometimes you don't realize the trash from your eyes.

2. How do you feel when you see others wasting food, and what thoughts does this provoke?

When you watch others, it hurts your soul. You can become aware of certain things. When you throw food away, you don't realize it. Instead of the food being used (e.g., donated), it's thrown away.

3. How does food waste align or conflict with your personal values (e.g., sustainability, resourcefulness, temperance-oriented behavior)?

It doesn't align with my personal values. I am a frugal person, and I don't like to throw away food or waste any resources. I'm a calculated person, so I believe it's worth calculating the impact of my actions.

4. What do you think about the resources (money, energy, labor, natural resources) that go into producing food that gets wasted, and how does that align with your sense of fairness or ethics?

From my point of view, there's not much I can do on a general level, only on a family level. It's a waste of the effort behind it. I think about the effort of the farmers, how dedicated they are, but when you throw it away, you don't think about that.

5. What do you think are the main causes of food waste (in your case and in general)?

- *Poor planning when buying food, purchases are often not intentional or calculated based on real needs.
- *Improper portioning when cooking or serving meals leads to unnecessary leftovers.
- *Neglecting to check expiration dates or food labels can result in items being wasted.
- *Failure to prioritize products with shorter shelf lives often causes them to expire before being used.
- *Overcooking or preparing excessive quantities, often driven by cravings or indulgence.
- *Impulsive decisions driven by momentary pleasures, without checking what's already available at home.
- *Infrequent but excessive grocery shopping, leading to spoilage before consumption.
- *Economic comfort contributes to over-purchasing without much concern for waste.
- *Oversized portions served in restaurants frequently result in uneaten food.
- *Supermarkets often encourage overbuying through large packaging and bulk offers.
- *Cultural traditions (such as holidays) encourage overabundance, rooted in longstanding habits.
- *Social pressures to impress guests by offering overly generous meals, aiming to display wealth or generosity.
- *A general lack of education and awareness about food waste and its environmental, social, and economic impacts.

II. See

What food waste patterns / behaviors do I see?

1. Have you noticed any behavior patterns (positive and negative) (please mention them) related to food waste that are common among people in your community or workplace?

Positive:

- *People go shopping more frequently and buy only what they need for one or two days, just the essentials.
- *Some people fast and thus eat more consciously.

Negative:

- *People throw away large portions at work and can't finish them.
- *Some foods, like fruits, are not stored properly, and then they spoil faster.
- *People who eat for pleasure and throw it away immediately.

2. What motivates people in your surroundings to minimize food waste?

- *Financial reasons, not everyone can afford to buy. We have a colleague who only eats at night, thinking about other priorities.
- *Health, eating more consciously.

3. Have you observed any external factors (e.g., portion sizes, expiration dates, packaging) leading to other people's food waste?

- *Portion sizes, from restaurants or supermarkets.
- *Food deals at the supermarkets.
- *Short expiration dates on products.
- *Unawareness of the difference between "best before" and "expiration date."

III. Say & Do

What do I say and do about food waste?

Own behavior:

1. Have you personally taken any steps to reduce food waste at home? If yes, what are they?

- *Freezing food to keep it as long as possible.
- *Checking expiration dates.
- *Planning meals and consuming them.
- *Preserving food in different forms so I don't throw it away (juices, compotes, jams).
- *Planning shopping.
- *More frequent shopping based on needs.

*Avoiding impulsive purchases.

*Eating food that has passed its expiration date, but I know it's still safe to eat.

Obstacles

2. What are your main obstacles or difficulties in trying to reduce your food waste?

*Cravings and desires, cooking fresh food while other items spoil.

*Sometimes, lack of time. I wasn't paying attention to labels many times.

*Lack of time to check all food and plan optimal consumption.

*Where I live. If I lived in the countryside, I would give food to an animal or, if the food was safe, I would try to donate it to the needy.

Motivations

3. What motivates you to avoid your food waste (e.g., saving money, protecting the environment)?

*Financial plan, to make as many savings as possible.

*Guilt of buying too much.

*Health.

*Not going shopping anymore.

IV. Hear

What do I hear about food waste?

1. Where do you get information about food waste and its impact (e.g., social media, news, campaigns)?

I don't inform myself on this topic. When I came into contact to it, it's through news and from the radio.

2. Have you ever been inspired by someone else's actions to reduce your food waste?

From my parents, from my grandparents, through the education I received. The lack of excess from my childhood inspired me to be as tight and economical as possible to avoid wasting food.

3. Please name two sources of information you trust most to help you avoid food waste.

My children and my family in general. I want to raise my family well-being.

Demographic variables:

Age: 50

Gender: Male

Education: University

Average monthly income for the whole family: more than 7001 lei/month

Residence: Urban

I have children: Yes

Religion: Christian Orthodox

P13

I. Think&Feel

What do I think and feel about food waste?

1. How do you feel when you throw away food (e.g., guilt, indifference, responsibility)?

If the food I throw away is not edible, then I feel comfortable. If it is and I happen to throw it away, then it hurts my soul. I don't like wasting food.

2. How do you feel when you see others wasting food, and what thoughts does this provoke?

I feel neutral, I don't want to judge. I don't watch at other's actions.

3. How does food waste align or conflict with your personal values (e.g., sustainability, resourcefulness, temperance-oriented behavior)?

It is important for me not to waste food, so it doesn't align with my personal values. However, in terms of moral values, it is not the most important issue.

4. What do you think about the resources (money, energy, labor, natural resources) that go into producing food that gets wasted, and how does that align with your sense of fairness or ethics?

I dislike industrialization. Excessive packaging bothers me. I try not to buy in excess and opt for local solutions, like shopping at markets.

5. What do you think are the main causes of food waste (in your case and in general)?

*Cultural aspects, for example, in Romania, where communism and shortages prevailed. Also, holidays and traditions where people often buy, eat, and waste excessively.

*Indifference stemming from a lack of education about food waste.

*An abundance of choices, which disconnects people from food and diminishes its value.

II. See

What food waste patterns / behaviors do I see?

1. Have you noticed any behavior patterns (positive and negative) (please mention them) related to food waste that are common among people in your community or workplace?

Positive:

-

Negative:

*Excessive shopping. People buy more than they need.

*The disappearance of small local stores.

*Unplanned shopping.

*The popularity of all-you-can-eat restaurants.

*Lack of time, which leads to rushing decisions and unconscious actions.

*At work, we order food from suppliers, and it is often wasted.

2. What motivates people in your surroundings to minimize food waste?

- *If there were penalties for wasting food.
- *Rationality—whether it makes sense or not.
- *Financial reasons.
- *Health—prioritizing quality over quantity.
- *Being part of a community where these issues are discussed.

3. Have you observed any external factors (e.g., portion sizes, expiration dates, packaging) leading to other people's food waste?

- *Packaging.
- *Shopping cart sizes.
- *The large size of supermarket checkout conveyor belts.
- *Expiration dates and labeling differences.
- *Marketing (discounts, promotions, special offers).

III. Say & Do

What do I say and do about food waste?

Own behavior:

1. Have you personally taken any steps to reduce food waste at home? If yes, what are they?

- *Shopping lists, planned purchases.
- *Food preservation (freezing).
- *Cooking simple recipes that don't require too many ingredients.
- *Frequent, smaller shopping trips based on actual needs.
- *Buying from local markets (emotional connection with food). Having an emotional connection with food creates a sense of guilt when wasting it. At the same time, buying from the market allows better control over the quantity of food purchased.
- *Meal planning.
- *Personal education on this topic.

Obstacles

2. What are your main obstacles or difficulties in trying to reduce your food waste?

*The way I was educated by my parents in this regard.

*Easy access to too many options, which sometimes leads to excessive buying.

*Food promotions that encourage over-purchasing.

Motivations

3. What motivates you to avoid your food waste (e.g., saving money, protecting the environment)?

*Respect for resources (we rarely waste food).

*Financial reasons.

*Environmental concerns.

*Health.

IV. Hear

What do I hear about food waste?

1. Where do you get information about food waste and its impact (e.g., social media, news, campaigns)?

I don't intentionally seek out information on this topic. Articles appear on my social media feeds, like Instagram or Facebook. The topic is also discussed within my company, thanks to the sustainability team.

2. Have you ever been inspired by someone else's actions to reduce your food waste?

Yes, I was inspired by my partner's actions, as he is more conscious and frugal. I was also inspired by my colleagues, who have more knowledge on this subject. The initiatives within my work team also influenced me.

3. Please name two sources of information you trust most to help you avoid food waste.

*AI tools like Copilot AI.

*My colleagues in the Sustainability team.

*Personal research, selecting what resonates with me.

Demographic variables:

Age: 40

Gender: Female

Education: University

Average monthly income for the whole family: more than 7001 lei/month

Residence: Urban

I have children: No

Religion: Christian Orthodox

P14

I. Think&Feel

What do I think and feel about food waste?

1. How do you feel when you throw away food (e.g., guilt, indifference, responsibility)?

I feel bad, it doesn't feel right. I worked hard for those resources, which cost money. Throwing away food and wasting it is not okay.

I also feel financial frustration. I'm frustrated that we don't have a pig, so we could avoid waste.

2. How do you feel when you see others wasting food, and what thoughts does this provoke?

I get angry because there are other ways to make use of food (for example, feeding animals).

3. How does food waste align or conflict with your personal values (e.g., sustainability, resourcefulness, temperance-oriented behavior)?

It's not right; it's a waste of natural resources.

4. What do you think about the resources (money, energy, labor, natural resources) that go into producing food that gets wasted, and how does that align with your sense of fairness or ethics?

So many resources are consumed, only for food to be disrespected in the end. It does not align with my values.

5. What do you think are the main causes of food waste (in your case and in general)?

*Not planning meals in advance.

*Excessive shopping. We throw away what expires.

*Unplanned purchases.

*The mindset shaped by our upbringing and culture: "Make more so there's enough."

II. See

What food waste patterns / behaviors do I see?

1. Have you noticed any behavior patterns (positive and negative) (please mention them) related to food waste that are common among people in your community or workplace?

Positive:

*Older people waste very little food; they value it more.

Negative:

*People are unaware. Many waste food without thinking.

*People are not emotionally connected to the food they buy.

*There is no discussion on this topic. There is no education about it.

2. What motivates people in your surroundings to minimize food waste?

*The education they received from their family.

*Moral values (common sense).

3. Have you observed any external factors (e.g., portion sizes, expiration dates, packaging) leading to other people's food waste?

*People in Romania and Moldova generally don't waste much due to tough living conditions. In fact, they sometimes trick you by giving you less food, not more.

III. Say & Do

What do I say and do about food waste?

Own behavior:

1. Have you personally taken any steps to reduce food waste at home? If yes, what are they?

- *Conscious and planned cooking, paying attention to portions and needs.
- *Planned shopping.
- *Buying less, more frequently.
- *Cooking with what's already in the house.
- *Freezing leftover food.
- *Consuming food if we still consider it safe (understanding the difference between best before and expiration date).

Obstacles

2. What are your main obstacles or difficulties in trying to reduce your food waste?

- *Fatigue
- *Lack of time
- *Unexpected situations

Motivations

3. What motivates you to avoid your food waste (e.g., saving money, protecting the environment)?

- *Financial reasons.
- *The negative effects of food waste (pollution, disease, etc.).
- *Empathy for those who have nothing.

IV. Hear

What do I hear about food waste?

1. Where do you get information about food waste and its impact (e.g., social media, news, campaigns)?

I don't seek out information on this topic, but received it sometimes on social media, news.

2. Have you ever been inspired by someone else's actions to reduce your food waste?

Yes, by informed public figures, my parents, and my grandparents.

3. Please name two sources of information you trust most to help you avoid food waste.

Nata Albot on YouTube and my family.

Demographic variables:

Age: 23

Gender: Female

Education: Student

Average monthly income for the whole family: 1001 - 3000 lei/month

Residence: Urban

I have children: No

Religion: Agnostic

P15

I. Think&Feel

What do I think and feel about food waste?

1. How do you feel when you throw away food (e.g., guilt, indifference, responsibility)?

I feel very guilty. That food could have been used in other ways. It could have been donated or given to animals.

2. How do you feel when you see others wasting food, and what thoughts does this provoke?

I feel bad. I don't blame them as much as I blame myself, but there should be more awareness on this topic.

3. How does food waste align or conflict with your personal values (e.g., sustainability, resourcefulness, temperance-oriented behavior)?

Food waste does not align with my values. I especially think about empathy for others, particularly those in need, and care for the environment.

4. What do you think about the resources (money, energy, labor, natural resources) that go into producing food that gets wasted, and how does that align with your sense of fairness or ethics?

A lot of effort and waste that could have been avoided.

5. What do you think are the main causes of food waste (in your case and in general)?

*Excessive shopping.

*Lack of awareness about the problems caused by food waste.

*Indifference—if it doesn't affect us directly, we don't care.

II. See

What food waste patterns / behaviors do I see?

1. Have you noticed any behavior patterns (positive and negative) (please mention them) related to food waste that are common among people in your community or workplace?

Positive:

*At work, our floor weighs the amount of food wasted every Friday.

*My colleagues are aware and want to take action—for example, they order one meal for two people instead of leaving food unfinished and wasted.

Negative:

*I still see a lot of food being thrown away out of indifference or ignorance.

2. What motivates people in your surroundings to minimize food waste?

- *Awareness of their contribution to a negative impact.
- *Influence from close people.
- *Regret about wasting something valuable.

3. Have you observed any external factors (e.g., portion sizes, expiration dates, packaging) leading to other people's food waste?

- *Portion sizes in supermarket-prepared meals.
- *Packaging.

III. Say & Do

What do I say and do about food waste?

Own behavior:

1. Have you personally taken any steps to reduce food waste at home? If yes, what are they?

- *Planned shopping (making a list).
- *Conscious shopping—buying based on need, in smaller and more frequent amounts.

Obstacles

2. What are your main obstacles or difficulties in trying to reduce your food waste?

- *My own organization.
- *Meal planning at times.
- *Lack of creativity—figuring out how to cook with leftovers.
- *Missing facilities that could help make better use of food.
- *My living situation (which prevents me from giving food to animals).

Motivations

3. What motivates you to avoid your food waste (e.g., saving money, protecting the environment)?

- *Using our resources optimally.
- *Reducing our negative impact on the environment.

*Acknowledging all the effort behind food production.

IV. Hear

What do I hear about food waste?

1. Where do you get information about food waste and its impact (e.g., social media, news, campaigns)?

I don't seek out information on this topic, but received it sometimes on social media, news, or through workshops at work.

2. Have you ever been inspired by someone else's actions to reduce your food waste?

I was inspired by my grandmother and my friends.

3. Please name two sources of information you trust most to help you avoid food waste.

I don't fully trust any particular source at the moment.

Demographic variables:

Age: 22

Gender: Female

Education: Student

Average monthly income for the whole family: 1001 - 3000 lei/month

Residence: Urban

I have children: No

Religion: Agnostic

P16

I. Think&Feel

What do I think and feel about food waste?

1. How do you feel when you throw away food (e.g., guilt, indifference, responsibility)?

I feel very sad. I feel a sense of grief and guilt, especially thinking about all the effort that went into bringing that food to us. Effort was made to produce it, we paid money for it, it took up space in the fridge—only to be thrown away.

2. How do you feel when you see others wasting food, and what thoughts does this provoke?

I feel that people are ungrateful for what they have and too easily discard resources. There are people in need who would love to have the security of knowing where their next meal comes from, yet they cannot, while others simply don't think and waste precious resources. I don't think it's fair, nor does it teach us to be more mindful and frugal.

3. How does food waste align or conflict with your personal values (e.g., sustainability, resourcefulness, temperance-oriented behavior)?

To avoid food waste, I become more creative and learn to cook new things with what I already have. It also awakens a sense of thriftiness in me, reminding me to be economical and moderate in order to manage resources wisely. Additionally, it's about respect for the resources consumed and the finite supplies that end up in our fridge.

4. What do you think about the resources (money, energy, labor, natural resources) that go into producing food that gets wasted, and how does that align with your sense of fairness or ethics?

I feel guilty when these resources go to waste. It's not ethical to throw food away so easily, especially when we could creatively repurpose it to consume less in the future. Money, energy, labor—it all goes to waste when food is discarded without a second thought.

It's not fair that some of us have too much and waste it, while others have too little and cannot get proper nutrition.

5. What do you think are the main causes of food waste (in your case and in general)?

*On a personal level, my lack of organization plays a role. I don't plan meals, I don't check the fridge before shopping, and I tend to buy whatever I feel like at the moment without considering what I already have at home. Another issue is that I often shop when I'm hungry, which increases the amount of food I purchase.

*On a general level, I think that a comfortable lifestyle can be a factor—when people live well, they tend to buy excessively without thinking about efficiency. When things come easily, they are discarded just as easily.

II. See

What food waste patterns / behaviors do I see?

1. Have you noticed any behavior patterns (positive and negative) (please mention them) related to food waste that are common among people in your community or workplace?

Positive:

*People take actions to preserve the food for a longer time (Ion's sister as an example).

Negative:

-

2. What motivates people in your surroundings to minimize food waste?

First and foremost, financial reasons. Food prices have gone up, so people think twice before overbuying. When things become expensive, people start cutting back.

3. Have you observed any external factors (e.g., portion sizes, expiration dates, packaging) leading to other people's food waste?

Often, restaurant portions are too large, and since food needs to be continuously rotated, a significant amount gets thrown away—whether customers come in or not.

III. Say & Do

What do I say and do about food waste?

Own behavior:

1. Have you personally taken any steps to reduce food waste at home? If yes, what are they?

I am consciously working on implementing solutions:

*Freezing and portioning food.

*Buying fewer but higher-quality products.

*Cooking fewer dishes and being more mindful by checking what's in the fridge first.

*Prioritizing products that are close to their expiration date.

*Doing planned grocery shopping on weekends.

*Using smaller cookware (pans and pots).

Obstacles

2. What are your main obstacles or difficulties in trying to reduce your food waste?

*Time constraints are the biggest issue. Work schedules and other responsibilities make the day hectic, draining energy that would otherwise help me be more mindful. Fatigue leads to convenience.

*Trying to impress others also leads to waste. Often, large meals are prepared for guests, and food is almost always left over and thrown away.

*Impulsive cravings when shopping lead to waste. I buy what I feel like eating at the moment and neglect what's already in the fridge.

*Supermarket promotions tempt me to buy more than I need.

Motivations

3. What motivates you to avoid your food waste (e.g., saving money, protecting the environment)?

*First and foremost, saving money.

*Gratitude for my current situation, recognizing the effort that goes into food production.

*The shame that comes with realizing there are people in need who struggle to find food while I waste it.

IV. Hear

What do I hear about food waste?

1. Where do you get information about food waste and its impact (e.g., social media, news, campaigns)?

I don't intentionally seek out information on this topic. I get information from friends, my children, and even from traditional teachings, which emphasize that wasting food is wrong.

2. Have you ever been inspired by someone else's actions to reduce your food waste?

Yes, I learned from my sister-in-law (Ion's sister) about freezing certain foods, such as beaten eggs. Since then, I've started dividing products into smaller portions and freezing them.

There was a saying in Moldova that, if food falls on the ground, you should pick it up and place it on a fence as a sign of respect for resources. Seeing this tradition in my community inspired me to uphold these values.

Additionally, my daughter keeps me informed about environmental issues, which motivates me to reduce waste.

3. Please name two sources of information you trust most to help you avoid food waste.

I would say my children, especially my daughter, because she stays well-informed, and my parents.

Demographic variables:

Age: 44

Gender: Female

Education: University

Average monthly income for the whole family: more than 7001 lei/month

Residence: Urban

I have children: Yes

Religion: Christian Orthodox

P17

I. Think&Feel

What do I think and feel about food waste?

1. How do you feel when you throw away food (e.g., guilt, indifference, responsibility)?

I feel guilty. I think about people who have nothing to eat, about the resources used throughout the food production process. I reflect on the education I received from my parents.

2. How do you feel when you see others wasting food, and what thoughts does this provoke?

I feel both responsibility and guilt, on behalf of us as humans. Seeing these behaviors makes me wonder why people act this way (out of carelessness, involuntarily, due to time constraints).

3. How does food waste align or conflict with your personal values (e.g., sustainability, resourcefulness, temperance-oriented behavior)?

This concept does not align with my personal values. I feel empathy for others and instinctively think about those in need. I believe in making use of resources rather than simply wasting them. For example, food could be given to animals instead of being thrown away.

4. What do you think about the resources (money, energy, labor, natural resources) that go into producing food that gets wasted, and how does that align with your sense of fairness or ethics?

I believe it is unfair that something as essential as food, which requires so much effort, is wasted. I see it as a lack of respect for those valuable resources. It reflects a loss of value that comes from our economic surplus.

5. What do you think are the main causes of food waste (in your case and in general)?

*Buying too much food.

*Lack of awareness of what we already have at home.

*Lack of knowledge about the problems caused by food waste.

*Failure to plan meals

*Sometimes, unexpected circumstances. For example, you plan to eat at home, but an opportunity arises to eat out instead.

II. See

What food waste patterns / behaviors do I see?

1. Have you noticed any behavior patterns (positive and negative) (please mention them) related to food waste that are common among people in your community or workplace?

Positive:

*At my workplace, I've noticed helpful initiatives regarding employee awareness of how much food is thrown away at the end of each week. Signs have been placed on every fridge on each floor, and the amount of discarded food is calculated every Friday.

*I have also seen donation initiatives in my community for those in need.

Negative:

*During holidays, a lot of food is cooked, eaten, and then wasted.

2. What motivates people in your surroundings to minimize food waste?

- *Financial reasons.
- *Helping those in need.
- *Health reasons (dieting).
- *The idea of not wasting and finding a useful way to repurpose leftovers.

3. Have you observed any external factors (e.g., portion sizes, expiration dates, packaging) leading to other people's food waste?

- *Portion sizes at restaurants. The good news is that portions have been reduced over time, likely for economic reasons.
- *Lack of education about food labels, such as the difference between "Best Before" and "Expiration Date."

III. Say & Do

What do I say and do about food waste?

Own behavior:

1. Have you personally taken any steps to reduce food waste at home? If yes, what are they?

- *I shop more consciously and no longer buy impulsively.
- *I plan meals in advance.
- I* consume food mindfully, paying attention to expiration dates and ensuring I eat what I buy in time.
- *If I have leftover ingredients, I try to get creative instead of buying more. I experiment with new recipes.

Obstacles

2. What are your main obstacles or difficulties in trying to reduce your food waste?

- *Cravings and impulse purchases.
- *The wide variety of food available to buy.
- *Shopping while tired.
- *Living in an apartment, which makes it harder to repurpose leftover food.

Motivations

3. What motivates you to avoid your food waste (e.g., saving money, protecting the environment)?

*Empathy for those who don't have the same opportunities as I do.

*Financial considerations.

*The education I received from my family.

IV. Hear

What do I hear about food waste?

1. Where do you get information about food waste and its impact (e.g., social media, news, campaigns)?

*From a nutritionist.

*Television.

*Social media.

*My personal trainer.

2. Have you ever been inspired by someone else's actions to reduce your food waste?

Yes, my family has inspired me to be mindful of resources. I've also been influenced by social media campaigns that talk about the impact of food waste.

3. Please name two sources of information you trust most to help you avoid food waste.

My parents and nutrition experts who talk about mindful consumption and how to avoid food waste.

Demographic variables:

Age: 34

Gender: Female

Education: University

Average monthly income for the whole family: 5001 - 7000 lei/month

Residence: Urban

I have children: No

Religion: Christian Orthodox

I. Think&Feel

What do I think and feel about food waste?

1. How do you feel when you throw away food (e.g., guilt, indifference, responsibility)?

I feel bad. I take some measures in this regard, but not enough. In recent years, my personal situation has improved.

2. How do you feel when you see others wasting food, and what thoughts does this provoke?

I feel understanding, but I try to raise awareness where I can. I speak empathetically and carefully because I care about the impact.

3. How does food waste align or conflict with your personal values (e.g., sustainability, resourcefulness, temperance-oriented behavior)?

Food waste does not align with my personal values. I spend a lot of time in nature (70% of my time) and care about the impact we have on it. Our footprint is significant, and we need to be more mindful of this.

4. What do you think about the resources (money, energy, labor, natural resources) that go into producing food that gets wasted, and how does that align with your sense of fairness or ethics?

It is not ethical for us to waste food after so much effort has gone into producing it and delivering it to us. I disagree with waste prevention systems both on a large and small scale. I would like to see more awareness on this topic.

5. What do you think are the main causes of food waste (in your case and in general)?

*Lack of education, leading to unconscious behaviors.

*People's indifference to issues that do not directly and obviously affect them.

*Convenience.

*Often, it is not done with bad intentions—it just happens due to lack of energy or time.

II. See

What food waste patterns / behaviors do I see?

1. Have you noticed any behavior patterns (positive and negative) (please mention them) related to food waste that are common among people in your community or workplace?

Positive:

*Some people refrain from wasting food due to social pressure, especially in groups that are informed on this topic.

Negative:

*People are in a hurry and don't find the time to educate themselves more about issues like this.

*Many people don't care unless they are directly affected—likely due to a lack of information and awareness.

*Food is often consumed for pleasure. People order out of curiosity and then waste it.

*Convenience and easy access to resources make it easy to make wasteful decisions.

*Some moral values are lacking, such as respect for resources, even without education or awareness of food waste.

*Shame is missing.

2. What motivates people in your surroundings to minimize food waste?

*The desire for self-improvement and becoming a better person.

*Concern for the planet.

*Awareness of the issue. The sustainability trend.

*The need to conform to a group.

*Wisdom that comes with age—understanding more over time.

3. Have you observed any external factors (e.g., portion sizes, expiration dates, packaging) leading to other people's food waste?

*Portion sizes.

*Lack of education about food labels.

*Packaging (if there is too much plastic, people may buy less to avoid waste).

*The appearance of food (whether fruits and vegetables look "perfect" or not).

III. Say & Do

What do I say and do about food waste?

Own behavior:

1. Have you personally taken any steps to reduce food waste at home? If yes, what are they?

*Conscious, planned shopping.

*Food preservation methods (dehydration, freezing).

Obstacles

2. What are your main obstacles or difficulties in trying to reduce your food waste?

*Inefficient organization.

*Changing work schedules.

*Occasionally shopping without a list.

Motivations

3. What motivates you to avoid your food waste (e.g., saving money, protecting the environment)?

*Environmental issues and their consequences.

*The desire to do better and have a positive impact on the world.

*Respect for the effort, resources, and time involved in food production.

IV. Hear

What do I hear about food waste?

1. Where do you get information about food waste and its impact (e.g., social media, news, campaigns)?

I don't actively seek information. I hear about it from friends, at work, on social media, and in podcasts.

2. Have you ever been inspired by someone else's actions to reduce your food waste?

My close circle has inspired me. Good actions in general motivate me to improve myself.

3. Please name two sources of information you trust most to help you avoid food waste.

I don't have a specific source, as I don't dig deeper into the topic. I would say my friends.

Demographic variables:

Age: 30

Gender: Male

Education: University

Average monthly income for the whole family: 5001 - 7000 lei/month

Residence: Urban

I have children: No

Religion: Agnostic

P19

I. Think&Feel

What do I think and feel about food waste?

1. How do you feel when you throw away food (e.g., guilt, indifference, responsibility)?

I feel guilty. I feel frustrated because the necessary infrastructure to meet people's needs is lacking. I try to minimize waste as much as possible. Whatever remains, I usually give to animals (ducks, chickens, dog). There is also the composting aspect—I keep eggshells.

2. How do you feel when you see others wasting food, and what thoughts does this provoke?

I feel responsible for others' carelessness, so I become vocal and start discussions. I also feel frustrated—I wish we would think more about this problem.

3. How does food waste align or conflict with your personal values (e.g., sustainability, resourcefulness, temperance-oriented behavior)?

I believe it aligns with many values instilled in me through my upbringing. First and foremost, respect for resources and effort. Empathy for rural people and their work.

4. What do you think about the resources (money, energy, labor, natural resources) that go into producing food that gets wasted, and how does that align with your sense of fairness or ethics?

I think about those who put in physical effort, and I want to support them. I buy locally from farmers. I do not promote supermarket food; instead, I think locally and respect the farmer who puts in so much care to produce food. I'm not sure if it's necessarily healthier, but I want to support local communities.

5. What do you think are the main causes of food waste (in your case and in general)?

- *Shopping without a plan.
- *Impulse buying in stores.
- *Going shopping while hungry.
- *Not checking the fridge before shopping.
- *Financial stability and easy access to a variety of products.

II. See

What food waste patterns / behaviors do I see?

1. Have you noticed any behavior patterns (positive and negative) (please mention them) related to food waste that are common among people in your community or workplace?

Positive:

- *Many people in my circle are trying to return to old habits—for example, baking bread at home and buying less.
- *They try to shop based on needs rather than impulsively. I see a wave of awareness about the value of food.
- *Another common pattern is that people are trying to grow their own food, whether it's something small in an apartment or a larger garden in their yard.

Negative:

*Throwing away food without thinking.

*Lack of knowledge about food labeling—misunderstanding the difference between "best before" and expiration dates.

*Overbuying—stocking up "just in case."

*Indifference toward food waste issues.

2. What motivates people in your surroundings to minimize food waste?

*Health reasons (body image and weight management).

*Financial reasons.

3. Have you observed any external factors (e.g., portion sizes, expiration dates, packaging) leading to other people's food waste?

*Oversized food portions that must be cooked before spoiling, but then end up being too much and get wasted.

*Cultural habits, such as holidays and barbecues, where excess food is common.

III. Say & Do

What do I say and do about food waste?

Own behavior:

1. Have you personally taken any steps to reduce food waste at home? If yes, what are they?

*Planned shopping and cooking.

*Buying locally and in small portions.

*Composting.

*Giving leftover food to animals.

Obstacles

2. What are your main obstacles or difficulties in trying to reduce your food waste?

*Where you live. When I lived in an apartment, it was complicated to implement anti-waste systems. There were no special containers for composting, for example.

*Lack of facilities.

*The effort required, especially during moments of fatigue.

*Access to specialized education (trustworthy sources of information).

Motivations

3. What motivates you to avoid your food waste (e.g., saving money, protecting the environment)?

*Personal values (respect for resources).

*Saving money.

IV. Hear

What do I hear about food waste?

1. Where do you get information about food waste and its impact (e.g., social media, news, campaigns)?

I try to inform about this topic. I get informed by friends, or at work by participating at anti-waste workshops.

2. Have you ever been inspired by someone else's actions to reduce your food waste?

Yes, I was inspired by the woman who held the food waste workshop at work. She presented options I wasn't aware of before. She encouraged us to give a second chance to foods that don't look perfect.

3. Please name two sources of information you trust most to help you avoid food waste.

First, my mother, because she reads a lot and analyzes information carefully. Second, podcasts with experts in the field, such as Laura Gavrilas from UMF. I also rely on my own instincts.

Demographic variables:

Age: 42

Gender: Female

Education: University

Average monthly income for the whole family: more than 7001 lei/month

Residence: Rural

I have children: Yes

Religion: Christian Orthodox

I. Think&Feel

What do I think and feel about food waste?

1. How do you feel when you throw away food (e.g., guilt, indifference, responsibility)?

I feel bad. Personally, I was taught not to waste anything. I was raised to eat everything and not throw food away. If it must be thrown away, then fine, but otherwise, it shouldn't be wasted.

2. How do you feel when you see others wasting food, and what thoughts does this provoke?

I feel sorry. That food could be used in a different way.

3. How does food waste align or conflict with your personal values (e.g., sustainability, resourcefulness, temperance-oriented behavior)?

I generally try to buy food in quantities that will be consumed quickly. I always try to purchase things I will actually use. Food waste does not align with my personal values. I buy consciously, thinking about what I really need.

4. What do you think about the resources (money, energy, labor, natural resources) that go into producing food that gets wasted, and how does that align with your sense of fairness or ethics?

These are resources that could be used for other necessities instead of being wasted. Why not estimate in advance how much one eats, how much one should eat, and how much is truly needed? We should consider multiple factors and safeguard essential resources.

5. What do you think are the main causes of food waste (in your case and in general)?

*Rushing.

*Satisfying other needs through food—compulsive buying to fill an internal void.

*Not knowing what you want, not having a shopping list, not buying consciously.

*Overbuying.

*Purchasing food out of curiosity just to try it.

*Buying low-quality food in larger quantities.

II. See

What food waste patterns / behaviors do I see?

1. Have you noticed any behavior patterns (positive and negative) (please mention them) related to food waste that are common among people in your community or workplace?

Positive:

*Buying fewer things to avoid waste.

Negative:

*Poorly cooked food that goes uneaten and is wasted.

*Wasting healthy food due to oversized portions.

*Leaving food uneaten simply because it is not liked.

2. What motivates people in your surroundings to minimize food waste?

*Economic motivation.

*The idea of saving—if you don't eat it today, you can eat it tomorrow.

*A sense of regret for wasted resources.

*The time and effort required to take out the trash.

3. Have you observed any external factors (e.g., portion sizes, expiration dates, packaging) leading to other people's food waste?

*Portion sizes.

*Oversized supermarket packaging.

III. Say & Do

What do I say and do about food waste?

Own behavior:

1. Have you personally taken any steps to reduce food waste at home? If yes, what are they?

- *We only cook what we need to eat.
- *Conscious shopping.
- *We experiment little and eat what we like.
- *Proper food storage methods.
- *Constantly checking food quality.
- *Cooking at home based on actual needs.
- *Creative cooking—repurposing leftovers.
- *Regularly measuring how much I need to eat.

Obstacles

2. What are your main obstacles or difficulties in trying to reduce your food waste?

- *Unexpected situations.
- *Living with other people.
- *Emotional eating—misjudging my level of hunger.

Motivations

3. What motivates you to avoid your food waste (e.g., saving money, protecting the environment)?

- *Saving money.
- *Saving time.
- *A sense of regret and ethical concerns.

IV. Hear

What do I hear about food waste?

1. Where do you get information about food waste and its impact (e.g., social media, news, campaigns)?

I intentionally seek out this information. Articles by nutritionists, journalists, social media, blogs, podcasts, and major journalistic outlets like The New York Times and The Guardian.

2. Have you ever been inspired by someone else's actions to reduce your food waste?

I have a level of discipline that allows me to develop my own system. I have taken ideas from various sources and adapted them for myself. There isn't a single person who inspired me—I have created my own nutrition plan and approach.

3. Please name two sources of information you trust most to help you avoid food waste.

Accredited scientific papers and social media.

Demographic variables:

Age: 26

Gender: Male

Education: University

Average monthly income for the whole family: 5001 - 7000 lei/month

Residence: Urban

I have children: No

Religion: Atheist

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I. Think&Feel

What do I think and feel about food waste?

1. How do you feel when you throw away food (e.g., guilt, indifference, responsibility)?

I feel guilty, ever since I was a child.

2. How do you feel when you see others wasting food, and what thoughts does this provoke?

I feel anxious and frustrated. I get extremely annoyed by such behavior and openly express my feelings with close people. With strangers, I don't intervene.

3. How does food waste align or conflict with your personal values (e.g., sustainability, resourcefulness, temperance-oriented behavior)?

It does not align. What bothers me the most is seeing people suffering and struggling financially (empathy). Sometimes, if food is still edible, I leave it near the trash bins so homeless people can take it. I also feel that the way we waste food out of thoughtlessness is unfair. It does not align with the education I received from my parents, which makes it impossible for me to remain indifferent when I see waste.

4. What do you think about the resources (money, energy, labor, natural resources) that go into producing food that gets wasted, and how does that align with your sense of fairness or ethics?

There are so many resources behind food production, and I feel it's a shame to throw food away just because of temporary emotions.

5. What do you think are the main causes of food waste (in your case and in general)?

*People's indifference.

*Convenience.

*Lack of meal planning and attention to already available food.

*Economic prosperity leading to excess.

*The wide variety of food options.

II. See

What food waste patterns / behaviors do I see?

1. Have you noticed any behavior patterns (positive and negative) (please mention them) related to food waste that are common among people in your community or workplace?

Positive:

Strong beliefs among people who care about the planet (sustainability group).

Negative:

- *People living in houses with yards throwing away food (e.g., cauliflower).
- *People with gardens throwing away branches instead of composting.
- *Lack of education.
- *Lack of awareness and unwillingness to engage with the topic due to personal comfort.

2. What motivates people in your surroundings to minimize food waste?

- *Empathy for others.
- *Financial considerations.
- *The effort behind earning money, which then gets wasted.

3. Have you observed any external factors (e.g., portion sizes, expiration dates, packaging) leading to other people's food waste?

*Oversized portions: I feel like there is positive progress here because people are becoming more aware that less but higher-quality food is better.

III. Say & Do

What do I say and do about food waste?

Own behavior:

1. Have you personally taken any steps to reduce food waste at home? If yes, what are they?

- *Organizing and planning the refrigerator.
- *Reminding family members about food waste.
- *Meal planning.
- *Freezing food.
- *Organizing food based on expiration dates.
- *Conscious, frequent, and small grocery shopping.
- *Making an effort to take excess food to the countryside or donate unprocessed cereals.

Obstacles

2. What are your main obstacles or difficulties in trying to reduce your food waste?

*Cooking too much.

Motivations

3. What motivates you to avoid your food waste (e.g., saving money, protecting the environment)?

*Concern for the environment and its resources.

*Financial reasons.

*The desire to be part of the solution, not the problem.

*The wish to help others.

IV. Hear

What do I hear about food waste?

1. Where do you get information about food waste and its impact (e.g., social media, news, campaigns)?

I do actively search for this type of data from:

*From work: the sustainability community.

*Documentaries on environmental topics.

*Social media.

2. Have you ever been inspired by someone else's actions to reduce your food waste?

Yes, by a workshop dedicated to food waste and by someone I know.

3. Please name two sources of information you trust most to help you avoid food waste.

I mostly research on my own. Another reliable source is the Sustainability team at work.

Demographic variables:

Age: 38

Gender: Female

Education: University

Average monthly income for the whole family: more than 7001 lei/month

Residence: Rural

I have children: Yes

Religion: Christian Orthodox

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I. Think&Feel

What do I think and feel about food waste?

1. How do you feel when you throw away food (e.g., guilt, indifference, responsibility)?

I feel guilty because I know I could have been more organized. Even though it happens rarely, I feel an emptiness in my stomach.

2. How do you feel when you see others wasting food, and what thoughts does this provoke?

The act itself saddens me. I don't know the reason behind it. Maybe they are unaware, maybe they were disorganized, or maybe they don't usually behave this way. Without knowing the reason, it's hard for me to say. I feel displeased thinking about the resources behind it. There are people who can't afford to eat, and then there are those who waste food.

3. How does food waste align or conflict with your personal values (e.g., sustainability, resourcefulness, temperance-oriented behavior)?

This concept does not align with my personal values. Therefore, I plan my meals quite well to avoid food waste. I throw away very little food. I am motivated by my concern for the environment, and I feel an emptiness in my stomach whenever I have to throw food away, whether it is wasteful or not. When I do discard food, I feel like I am not doing things right, and I think about those who don't have access to food. I have respect for the resources behind food production, and although my feelings don't directly solve the problem, it still pains me. Perhaps the food could have stayed on supermarket shelves, and the surplus could have been donated to food banks. In some countries, supermarkets have initiatives where they place food close to expiration on special shelves, allowing people to take it for free. It would be great if such practices existed, so food could be donated before it becomes inedible.

Other initiatives from other countries: dumpster diving.

4. What do you think about the resources (money, energy, labor, natural resources) that go into producing food that gets wasted, and how does that align with your sense of fairness or ethics?

It is definitely an ethical issue. On one hand, some people don't have enough resources because they are unevenly distributed. Even if they were distributed fairly, some people still might not be able to afford them. On the other hand, there is the issue of resources. We use finite resources, exploit them, and then, either consciously or unconsciously, waste food and everything behind it. This leads to issues such as excessive water consumption, arable land use, deforestation, and animal farming. There is a huge impact on biodiversity, as well as pollution of soil, groundwater, and more.

5. What do you think are the main causes of food waste (in your case and in general)?

*Rushing, lack of time.

*Lack of awareness in certain situations. Indifference, lack of education, lack of information.

*Lack of responsibility.

*Oversupply (we have access to too much, which devalues it).

*Indifference toward the topic—if it doesn't affect you, it doesn't exist.

*Lack of knowledge on food storage (e.g., herbs). People don't always know the best preservation and storage methods. If you have something in surplus, you can preserve it and use it later.

II. See

What food waste patterns / behaviors do I see?

1. Have you noticed any behavior patterns (positive and negative) (please mention them) related to food waste that are common among people in your community or workplace?

Positive:

*Unexpectedly high interest from colleagues in fighting food waste.

*Meals with lower-quality ingredients.

*Community orchard—people work on it and then take what they need.

*Workplace initiatives.

*Composting project (Cluj).

*An app that connects people who compost in Cluj. Organic waste for composting.

*Bonapp.

*Supermarkets using near-expired food for sauces, pasta, etc.

Negative:

*Forgetting about food in the fridge until it's no longer consumable.

*People ordering too much food and not being able to eat it (packaging that then needs to be recycled). Oversized portions that sit in the fridge.

*We don't know how to estimate portions. We don't know how much we need.

*No visible campaigns about this. No guidance on where to place food in the fridge for better storage.

2. What motivates people in your surroundings to minimize food waste?

*Financial reasons.

*Reducing environmental impact.

*Social aspect—empathy toward those in need.

3. Have you observed any external factors (e.g., portion sizes, expiration dates, packaging) leading to other people's food waste?

*There are still alternative options in stores.

*Restaurant and food delivery portions are too large.

*Default cutlery included in deliveries.

*Lack of education on the subject.

*Food that doesn't look perfect but is still usable.

III. Say & Do

What do I say and do about food waste?

Own behavior:

1. Have you personally taken any steps to reduce food waste at home? If yes, what are they?

*Buying small portions.

- *Paying extra for sustainable options.
- *Supporting a community sustainability program. I receive a box of food every two weeks, which makes me cook more so that nothing goes to waste.
- *Looking for innovative food preservation methods.
- *Cooking creatively.
- *Freezing food.
- *Sharing large portions with people I know won't waste them (e.g., Daniela and Emil's mother).
- *Planned shopping.
- *Prioritizing leftover food from previous days.
- *Cooking frequently.
- *Diversifying meals—helps me waste less food. If you don't experiment, you end up discarding certain ingredients. (Example: mint tea bags for cooking. I once threw away fennel.)
- *Educating my partner.
- *Buying imperfect fruits and vegetables.
- *Buying local whenever possible—less waste.

Obstacles

2. What are your main obstacles or difficulties in trying to reduce your food waste?

- *Lack of time and energy. I don't have enough information on food preservation—it's a complex topic with many variables.
- *Lack of more intensive education.
- *No easy composting method available.
- *Restaurants and food delivery services not allowing customers to use their own containers.
- *Default packaging.
- *Lack of meal and shopping planning.
- *Limited food options for vegans—sometimes I have to buy meals with ingredients I don't like, leading to selective eating and waste.

Motivations

3. What motivates you to avoid your food waste (e.g., saving money, protecting the environment)?

- *Environmental impact.
- *Financial reasons.
- *Empathy toward those in need—morally speaking.

*Past experiences.

*Respect for labor, resources, and people. I'm concerned about biodiversity. How easily we cut down forests for palm oil, soy, cocoa, etc.

*My visit to South Africa for a conference—seeing the lack of water resources and drought. Being asked to take short showers.

*The excessive production of chemicals. Wasting resources for no reason.

IV. Hear

What do I hear about food waste?

1. Where do you get information about food waste and its impact (e.g., social media, news, campaigns)?

I actively seek out information about this topic, usually from EU websites, statistics, and food banks in Romania. WinNow, social media, World Economic Forum, scientific articles, and close acquaintances.

2. Have you ever been inspired by someone else's actions to reduce your food waste?

Yes, my workplace colleague's passion and her master's project on small producers' issues. Also, Mrs. Maria, the cleaner, and the WinNow team.

3. Please name two sources of information you trust most to help you avoid food waste.

*Food Safety & Food Waste, EU

*Scientific articles without conflicts of interest (veganism, food production)

Demographic variables:

Age: 35

Gender: Female

Education: University

Average monthly income for the whole family: 5001 - 7000 lei/month

Residence: Urban

I have children: No

Religion: Agnostic